

GENERAL COMMENTS ABOUT THE LIFE OF SUFI OLLOYAR

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Sufi Olloyar is one of our major scholars who gained wide fame as a mystic poet and writer among the peoples of Turkestan. The name of the pure breed is Olloyar, and the name of the corrupt father is Allahkuli. The title of Sufi was given to him for his faith and services in the path of Sharia and Tariqah.

According to the book "Risalai Aziza" (commentary on Sufi Olloyar's work "Sabotu-l-ojizin") published in Kazan in 1797 by the son of Tatar historian Tajiddin Yolchigul, Sofi Olloyar was born in 1644. Descendants of Sufi Olloyar, as well as academician B. Valikhojhaev, professor B. Hasanov, Professor Sh. According to the latest information of Sirojiddinov and others, it is noted that Sofi Olloyar was born in 1634. If we take into account that the great Sufi lived 90 years according to the Hijri-lunar calculation, and 87 years according to the Christian calculation, it becomes clear that his date of birth is 1634.

Information about the personal life of Sufi Olloyar is scattered in his works. According to the work "Risalai Aziza", the poet was born in 1634 in the village of Minglar, belonging to the Mionkol region, and belongs to the Otarchi clan of the Chinese-Kipchak tribe.

Sufi Olloyar also repeatedly mentioned that he was from the Otarchi clan of Miyonkol oasis:

Although Olloyar Otarchi is bad,
Koymagil fell into the hands of the enemy.
or

Although Olloyor O'tarchidur, erur ul is also bad,
It's a time when he died for a few.

In these verses, Oloyor explained to which tribe he belongs, and also that he is a passer-by in this world. He pointed to the impermanence of the world.

Academician Vahid Abdullaev noted the following thoughts: We, a group of intellectuals, visited the grave of Sufi Olloyor, a mystic poet and scientist, in the village of Katta Vakhshivor, Oltinsoy district, Surkhandarya region. We got to know the descendants of Sofi Oloyor. We talked with Sufi Olloyar's son Siddiq Muhammad, his son Khojakalon, his son Eshan Khan, his son Khalil Khan and Umar Khan, Kokil Khan, and Karimat Khan, Muzaffar Khan, who are considered to be their descendants.

He studied at the mosque school in the village of Sheikhs (the current village of Sheikhs in Ishtikhan district), then went to Bukhara and was educated at the dargah of the Sheikhs of Dzhoybor. There, he married three times, served several times in the tax collector's court, eventually sought a murid, rose to the rank of sheikh, and with the intention of expanding his influence and spreading the religious ideology among the masses, "Sabat ul-Ojizin", "Muradil-Arifin", " He wrote books such as "Tuhfatut-talibin", "Maslak ul-Muttaqin".

In particular, literary scholar I. Based on what was said, Suvankulov judges it as ishtikhon and tries to popularize it in his research. There are claims that "Sufi Olloyor is from Miyonkol oasis." It is known from history that Miyonkol oasis included the lands located between Samarkand and Bukhara, more precisely, the lands located around Zarafshan of Karmana, Narpay, Kattakurgan and Ishtikhon districts of today's Samarkand region. Fahmi's tazkir written in 1277 Hijri, 1860 AD states: "Sufi Olloyar Samarkandi Sheikh Dilafroz is one of the famous caliphs of Sufi Navroz. He is the author of the books "Maslakul-muttaqin", "Sabot ul- ojizin", "Makhzanul-mute'in", "Murod ul-orifin".

Sufi Olloyor received his primary education in the village of Otarchi, and

studied in Bukhara madrasas at the age of 10-12. He was brought up in the school of Dzhoybor sheikhs, who had a great position and prestige in the Emirate of Bukhara, and received an excellent education for his time in religious and secular sciences. According to Sufi Olloyar's confession, he was mentored by two people in the science of jurisprudence: Khwaja Mo'min and Muhammad Ghazni. wishes

The mystic poet and scientist mentioned that he belongs to the Naqshbandi sect in the praise section of the book "Maslak ul-Muttaqin". According to his confession, the previous piri murshidi, who sent him to the tariqat, taught him the secrets of Sufism, the ravish of spirit, was Khoja Navro'z from Shahrissab. Later, the famous Naqshbandi sheikh of Bukhara, Habibullah, joined Eshan and served him and reached the rank of sheikh.

A sharp positive change in the life and worldview of Sufi Olloyar happened after meeting one of the virtuous and learned people of his time, Sheikh Navroz. His pure name is Navroz. He was burning with the love of God from head to toe. Also, Sufi Olloyar's meeting with the famous Sufism sheikh Ofaqkhoja had a strong influence on his spiritual and moral life.

The poet spends most of his life in the Sufi guzar of the city of Kattakorgan. Then he lived in Chonqaymish corner of Jom mountain, then in Qabadiyan (1710), then in Katta Vakhshivor settlement of Surkhandarya region, Dehnav district (now Oltinsoy district).

After his studies, Navqiran Olloyar was in public service for a short time among the tax collectors of Abdulaziz Khan's palace. However, he voluntarily left this service, under the influence of the sheikhs of Khojbor and his own faith, he became a murid of Navruz Eshan, one of the leaders of Islamic teachings in Bukhara, and devoted his life to the path of Naqshbandiyya.

In the Persian work "Maslak ul-Muttaqin" by Sufi Olloyar, about Hazrat Navroz:

I was in the service of the King of Asr (Khan of Bukhara) Abdulaziz Khan

(1645-1680), and the bread I ate was poison. Suddenly, by the grace of Allah, I became attached to the love of the Most High.

The blessed name of the murshid who is next to the beloved of Allah is Navruz, and it is a word of pain from head to foot. It is difficult to describe his qualities. His passion was so strong that the most delicate veins and every hair was moved. I immediately knelt at his feet and shook his hand.

During the reign of Abdulaziz Khan (1645-1680), when he was about 25 years old, he was appointed to the position of the court of tax collectors for a certain period. It was a big practice at that time. The poet, who sincerely entered the position of the Tora, saw a lot of injustices and oppression in this field, and eventually he voluntarily gave up this duty.

However, Oloyor worked very hard in his position as a tory for some time. His righteousness and cruelty to his enemies reaches such a level that people tremble with fear when they hear the name of Oloyor Tora. Once, one of Sheikh Habibullah's caliphs severely punished him for not paying the tax on a bag of goods he brought to Roston market in Bukhara.

Hearing this situation, Sheikh Habibullah asked Olloyor to return from this path. According to another legend, Oloyor wore a sheep's belly on his head and wrapped its intestines around his neck and walked the streets of Bukhara in order to get rid of his excessive arrogance. People who saw this situation agreed that Oloyor was crazy. After that, Sheikh Habibullah goes to the dargah. As mentioned, during the period of working in the tax court, he saw many injustices and oppression of the people. Later, in the passage of "Maslaku-l-Muttaqin" under the title "Dar bayani va khalal kardan az narasaikhoi hud, yo, Allah" he gives the following information about his biography:

"I confess to all my sins, but I am unable to punish them all. Because I am not one of the istifada (excusable) people; I am not a master, mir, or prince. If you ask me about my past life, you will be scared and turn away from me. I have been

in the service of the king of the age, I have eaten the bread of various peoples. But those breads were a product of taste. I won't say more than that. It was my habit to sit in sorrow, sadness was high and my thoughts were low. Food turned into poison in my mouth, such was the horizon of our life in the city. It was customary to flatter every official with a smile on his face! ".